

CAMPANA SEPARABLE RATIONAL CONNECTEDNESS OF TORIC ORBIFOLD

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ABSTRACT. We prove that smooth non-klt toric orbifolds are separably Campana rationally connected, extending [CLT25, Corollary 8.4] which treats the klt case. We also show that there always exists a positive characteristic in which a singular weighted projective space, viewed as a non-klt Campana orbifold, is not separably Campana rationally connected.

1. INTRODUCTION

A Campana orbifold is a pair (X, Δ_ϵ) consisting of a projective variety X and a \mathbb{Q} -divisor Δ_ϵ with coefficients between 0 and 1. The flexibility imposed by the coefficients of the boundary divisor allows the orbifold structure to interpolate between projective ($\Delta_\epsilon = 0$) and quasi-projective varieties (all coefficients of Δ_ϵ are 1), and many classical questions in birational and arithmetic geometry naturally admit analogues in the orbifold setting. An important example of these questions centers around the geometry of Campana rationally connected orbifolds. Broadly speaking, a Campana orbifold (X, Δ_ϵ) is said to be Campana rationally connected if any two points of X can be connected by a rational curve intersecting the boundary Δ_ϵ in a controlled way. Campana conjectured that the rational connectedness nature of an orbifold should be determined by the positivity of its log anticanonical bundle:

Conjecture 1.1 (Campana). Let (X, Δ_ϵ) be a klt Fano orbifold over an algebraically closed field \mathbf{k} of characteristic zero, i.e. (X, Δ_ϵ) is a klt Campana orbifold such that $-(K_X + \Delta_\epsilon)$ is ample. Then (X, Δ_ϵ) is Campana rationally connected.

Recently, the authors in [CLT25] furnished Campana's orbifold theory using the framework of logarithmic geometry. They showed that Campana rational connectedness holds for smooth Campana toric orbifolds, thereby providing concrete examples in which the conjecture is satisfied. In fact, they further proved that these orbifolds are separably Campana rationally connected.

1.1. Main results. Over a field of characteristic zero, rationally connected varieties can be regarded as higher dimensional analogues of rational surfaces. In positive characteristic, the appropriate notion is separable rational connectedness. We show that smooth Campana toric orbifolds are also separably Campana rationally connected in the non-klt setting (see Remark 2.10), that is, when the boundary divisor contains a component with coefficient one:

Theorem 1.2 (Theorem 3.1 and Corollary 3.3). *Let (X, Δ_ϵ) be a Campana toric orbifold over an algebraically closed field \mathbf{k} of characteristic $p > 0$. Suppose there exists a smooth cone in the fan defining X such that all of its adjacent cones are smooth. Then (X, Δ_ϵ) is separably Campana rationally connected.*

The klt case has been proven in [CLT25, Corollary 8.4], but our proof extends to the non-klt case. When X is a toric surface, we characterize the failure of separability in terms of its singularities (cf. Definition 4.4).

Theorem 1.3 (Theorem 4.6). *Let (X, Δ_ϵ) be a non-klt Campana toric surface orbifold over an algebraically closed field k of characteristic $p > 0$. If every ray of the fan of X has a non-adjacent cone which is either smooth or tamely singular, then (X, Δ_ϵ) is separably Campana rationally connected.*

Finally, we discuss the failure of separability when X is a singular weighted projective space.

Theorem 1.4 (Theorem 4.12). *Let k be an algebraically closed field of characteristic $p > 0$. Let (X, Δ) be a non-klt Campana toric orbifold over k such that X is a weighted projective space $\mathbb{P}(q_0, \dots, q_n)$ and every component of Δ has coefficient one. If p divides one of the weights q_j , then (X, Δ) is not separably Campana rationally connected.*

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2. BACKGROUND

Through out the paper, we work over an algebraically closed field k . Given a log scheme X with log structure \mathcal{M}_X , we denote by \underline{X} its underlying scheme.

2.1. Stable log map. In this section, we briefly recall the definitions of stable log maps and contact order, which play a central role in the notion of Campana rational connectedness. Although these concepts arise from log geometry, in the toric setting they admit explicit combinatorial descriptions, which we use throughout this paper. We refer the interested reader to [CLT25, Sections 2 and 3] for additional details.

Definition 2.1. A *log curve* over a log scheme S is a pair

$$(\pi : C \rightarrow S, \{p_1, \dots, p_n\})$$

satisfying the following conditions

1. The underlying pair $(\underline{\pi} : \underline{C} \rightarrow \underline{S}, \{p_1, \dots, p_n\})$ is a family of pre-stable curves over \underline{S} with n marked points.
2. π is proper, log smooth, and integral.
3. If $U \subset \underline{C}$ is the smooth locus of $\underline{\pi}$, then $\mathcal{M}_C|_U \cong \underline{\pi}^* \overline{\mathcal{M}}_S \oplus \bigoplus_{k=1}^n p_{k*} \mathbb{N}_{\underline{S}}$.

Definition 2.2. A *log map* over X is a morphism of log schemes $f : C \rightarrow X$ such that $\pi : C \rightarrow S$ is a log curve over S . A log map is *stable* if the underlying map \underline{f} is stable in the usual sense.

Given a stable log map $f : C \rightarrow X$, we say f is *non-degenerate* if S is a log point with the trivial log structure. By [Kat00], this implies that the underlying curve \underline{C} is an irreducible smooth curve and \mathcal{M}_C is the divisorial structure given by the marked points. Furthermore, given that the dense open subscheme of \underline{C} where the log structure is trivial is sent by \underline{f} to the dense open $X \setminus \Delta$, we can conclude that $f(C) \not\subset \Delta$. In particular, $f^{-1}(\Delta) \subset \{p_1, \dots, p_n\}$.

2.2. Contact order. Let \underline{X} be a projective toric variety. Let M be the lattice of characters and N its dual lattice. We endow \underline{X} with the divisorial log structure induced by its toric boundary Δ , i.e. \mathcal{M}_X is the subsheaf of \mathcal{O}_X consisting of regular functions which are invertible on $\underline{X} \setminus \Delta$. We write X for the induced log scheme. We let $\Sigma^{(1)} \subset \Sigma$ denote the collection of the rays of the fan Σ of \underline{X} . For each $\rho_i \in \Sigma^{(1)}$, let $u_{\rho_i} \in \rho_i \cap N$ denote its lattice generator and let Δ_i be

the corresponding torus invariant divisor (we often abuse ρ_i for its ray generator). We write $\Delta = \sum_{\rho_i \in \Sigma^{(1)}} \Delta_i$.

Let $f : C \rightarrow X$ be a non-degenerate stable log map with marked points p_1, \dots, p_n . The contact order at p_i is given by

$$\overline{\mathcal{M}}_{X, f(p_i)} \longrightarrow \overline{\mathcal{M}}_{C, p_i} \cong \mathbb{N}.$$

The point $f(p_i)$ lies in a unique torus orbit corresponding to some cone $\tau \in \Sigma$. The log structure of X in a neighborhood of $f(p_i)$ is induced by the affine toric variety $X_\tau = \text{Spec } \mathbf{k}[M \cap \tau^\vee]$. In particular

$$\overline{\mathcal{M}}_{X, f(p_i)} = \overline{\mathcal{M}}_{X_\tau, f(p_i)} \simeq (M \cap \tau^\vee) / (M \cap \tau^\vee)^\times.$$

We deduce that:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Hom}(\overline{\mathcal{M}}_{X_\tau, f(p_i)}, \mathbb{N}) &\simeq \text{Hom}((M \cap \tau^\vee) / (M \cap \tau^\vee)^\times, \mathbb{N}) \\ &\simeq \text{Hom}(M \cap \tau^\vee, \mathbb{N}) \\ &\simeq \mathbb{N} \cap \tau \subset \mathbb{N}. \end{aligned}$$

More generally, the set of possible contact orders at a marked point is in bijection with the lattice points in the support of the fan of X .

Proposition 2.3 (Balancing condition). [CLS11, Proposition 6.4.1] *The collection of contact orders $\{c_k\}_{k=1}^n$ determined by $f : C \rightarrow X$ satisfies the balancing condition:*

$$(1) \quad \sum_{k=1}^n c_k = \sum_{i,k} c_{k,i} u_{\rho_i} = 0$$

Example 2.4. Let X be \mathbb{P}^m endowed with the log structure induced by its toric boundary Δ given by $\rho_0, \dots, \rho_m \in \Sigma^{(1)}$. Let H_i be the hyperplane section corresponding to ρ_i . We have $\sum_{i=0}^m u_{\rho_i} = 0$. Let $f : C \rightarrow \mathbb{P}^1$ be a non-degenerate stable log map and let β denote its curve class in X and a collection of non-zero lattice points $\varsigma = \{c_k \in \mathbb{N}\}_k$, where each c_k specifies the contact order at the k -th marking p_k . By smoothness of X , There is a unique presentation

$$c_k = \sum_{i=0}^m c_{k,i} u_{\rho_i}.$$

The balancing condition (1) is a consequence of the intersection-theoretic constraints:

$$\sum_{k=1}^n c_{k,i} = H_i \cdot \beta.$$

2.3. Campana Rational Connectedness for toric orbifolds. In this section, we recall the notion of Campana rational connectedness. We first adapt the definition of a Campana orbifold ([CLT25, Definition 5.1]) to the toric case.

Definition 2.5 (Campana toric orbifold). Let X be a projective toric variety with toric boundary $\Delta = \bigcup_i \Delta_i$. Let X be the induced log scheme. To each irreducible component Δ_i , we assign a weight

$$\epsilon_i = 1 - \frac{1}{m_i}$$

where $m_i \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1} \cup \{\infty\}$. Define the \mathbb{Q} -divisor

$$\Delta_\epsilon = \sum_i \epsilon_i \Delta_i$$

The pair (X, Δ_ϵ) is called a *Campana toric orbifold*. If $\epsilon_i \neq 1$ for all i , (X, Δ_ϵ) is called a *klt Campana toric orbifold*. Otherwise, it is called a non-klt Campana toric orbifold. If all coefficients are ∞ , we say that it is an *absolute non-klt Campana orbifold*.

Definition 2.6. [CLT25, Definition 5.2] Let (X, Δ_ϵ) be a Campana toric orbifold. Let $f : C \rightarrow X$ be a stable log map over a log point S . Denote $c_{k,i}$ the multiplicity of the i -th component Δ_i along the k -th marked point, and let $\varsigma = \{c_{k,i}\}$ be the set of contact orders. We say that ς is of *Campana type* if

1. When $m_i < \infty$, every index k satisfies either $c_{k,i} = 0$ or $c_{k,i} \geq m_i$.
2. When $m_i = \infty$, there is at most one index k with $c_{k,i} > 0$.

Definition 2.7 (Campana rational connectedness). [CLT25, Definitions 4.1 and 5.6] Let X be the log scheme over \mathbf{k} induced by a projective toric variety of dimension d with toric boundary Δ . We say that X is (separably) rationally ς -connected if there is a family of genus zero non-degenerate stable log maps $\pi : \mathcal{U} \rightarrow W$, $ev : \mathcal{U} \rightarrow X$ with contact orders ς and such that $\underline{\mathcal{U}} = W \times \mathbb{P}^1$ and $ev^{(2)} : \mathcal{U} \times_W \mathcal{U} = W \times \mathbb{P}^1 \times \mathbb{P}^1 \rightarrow X \times X$ is dominant (and separable). Moreover, we say that (X, Δ_ϵ) is (separably) *Campana rationally connected* if there exists a collection of contact orders ς of Campana type such that X is (separably) ς -rationally connected. When all non-zero contact orders of ς are not divisible by $\text{char } \mathbf{k}$, we say (X, Δ_ϵ) is (separably) Campana rationally connected by good contact orders.

When \mathbf{k} is uncountable, rational connectedness is equivalent to the geometric condition that for a general pair of points $x, y \in X$, there is a log map $f : \mathbb{P}^1 \rightarrow X$ with contact order ς satisfying $x, y \in f(\mathbb{P}^1)$. When (X, Δ_ϵ) is a Campana toric orbifold, the authors gave a sufficient combinatorial condition for Campana rational connectedness in terms of contact orders and the lattice.

Theorem 2.8. [CLT25, c.f. Theorem 8.2] Let \underline{X} be a projective toric variety of dimension d with toric boundary Δ . Let ς be a collection of positive contact orders satisfying the balancing condition. Then

- (a) If the sub-lattice $\mathbb{Z} \cdot \varsigma \subset \mathbb{N}$ is of rank d , X is rationally ς -connected.
- (b) If $\mathbb{Z} \cdot \varsigma$ is of rank d , and $\mathbb{N}/(\mathbb{Z} \cdot \varsigma)$ contains no $\text{char } \mathbf{k}$ -torsion, then X is separably rationally ς -connected.

Note that the original theorem is stated with \underline{X} being smooth and Δ being SNC, but as mentioned in [CLT25, Remark 8.3], these assumptions are not necessary. In particular, any klt Campana toric orbifold is Campana rationally connected by good contact orders:

Corollary 2.9. [CLT25, Corollary 8.4] Endow the toric variety \underline{X} of Theorem 2.8 with the log structure induced by Δ and consider a Campana klt toric orbifold (X, Δ_ϵ) . Then (X, Δ_ϵ) is separably Campana rationally connected by good contact orders.

Remark 2.10. As noted in [CLT25, Remark 5.3], the definition of Campana rational connectedness in the non-klt case (Definition 2.6) is weaker than the one present in the literature. When the multiplicities of a boundary component Δ_i satisfy $m_i = \infty$, the classical definition (c.f. [Cam11, Definition 9.4]) asserts that $f(\mathbb{P}^1) \subset X \setminus \Delta_i$. On the other hand, one can follow the definition in the arithmetic setting: the exact analogy is to fix a finite set S of closed points in \mathbb{P}^1 and to insist that the image $f(\mathbb{P}^1)$ can only intersect the boundary Δ_i at these closed points. However, as shown in the next example, this definition would be again too rigid, and hence justifies the current choice.

Example 2.11. Let $n \geq 3$ and (\mathbb{P}^n, Δ) be a Campana absolute non-klt toric orbifold. Then (\mathbb{P}^n, Δ) is not Campana rationally connected in the classical sense. Indeed, if ς is a set of contact

orders making (\mathbb{P}^n, Δ) Campana rationally connected, then the classical definition forces us to send $|\zeta| = n + 1$ many points of the curve to Δ . Then the proof of [CLT25, Theorem 8.2] shows that the parameter space of the family $\pi : \mathcal{U} \rightarrow \mathcal{W}$ making (\mathbb{P}^n, Δ) Campana rationally connected has dimension n . In particular, the evaluation map $\text{ev}^{(2)}$ is not dominant.

3. SMOOTH CAMPANA NON-KLT TORIC ORBIFOLD

In this section, we show that a smooth Campana non-klt toric orbifold is separably Campana rationally connected, extending [CLT25, Corollary 8.4] (cf. Corollary 2.9) which treats the klt case. Throughout the section, we assume that the base field \mathbf{k} is algebraically closed of characteristic $p > 0$.

Theorem 3.1. *Let (X, Δ_ϵ) be a Campana smooth toric orbifold. Then it is separably Campana rationally connected.*

Proof. Let $\dim(X) = d$. We first prove the statement when (X, Δ_ϵ) is absolute non-klt. Choose a maximal cone σ of the fan and reorder the primitive rays so that the first d columns of the ray matrix

$$R = [\rho_1 \cdots \rho_n] \in M_{d \times n}(\mathbb{Z})$$

are the rays of σ . We will prove that there exists $a_1, \dots, a_n \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ such that if L is the lattice generated by the $a_i \rho_i$'s, then:

$$(2) \quad \sum_{i=1}^n a_i \rho_i = 0,$$

$$(3) \quad \text{rank}(L) = d,$$

$$(4) \quad \text{and } \mathbb{Z}^d / L \text{ has no } p\text{-torsion}$$

and then conclude using Theorem 2.8. Write

$$R = [B \mid A], \quad B \in GL_d(\mathbb{Z}), \quad A \in M_{d \times (n-d)}(\mathbb{Z}),$$

so B is invertible by smoothness of σ . Solutions of $Rc = 0$ are parameterized by $c = (c_B, c_A) \in \mathbb{Z}^d \times \mathbb{Z}^{n-d}$ with

$$Bc_B + Ac_A = 0 \quad \iff \quad c_B = -B^{-1}Ac_A,$$

Consider the induced \mathbb{F}_p -linear map

$$\Phi : (\mathbb{F}_p)^{n-d} \longrightarrow (\mathbb{F}_p)^d, \quad \Phi(\overline{c_A}) = -\overline{B}^{-1} \overline{A} \overline{c_A},$$

and write $V = \text{im } \Phi \subset (\mathbb{F}_p)^d$. It is enough to show that there exists $v \in V$ with all coordinates non-zero in \mathbb{F}_p . Indeed, assume such v exists and let $\overline{c_A} \in (\mathbb{F}_p)^{n-d}$ such that $\Phi(\overline{c_A}) = v$. Lift $\overline{c_A}$ to any integer vector $c_A \in \mathbb{Z}^{n-d}$. Set $c_B := -B^{-1}Ac_A \in \mathbb{Z}^d$ and $c = (c_B, c_A) \in \mathbb{Z}^n$. Then, by construction, $Rc = 0$. In particular, if $c = (c_1, \dots, c_n)$, we have

$$\sum_{i=1}^n c_i \rho_i = 0.$$

On the other hand, by convex geometry, since X is projective, there exists $c'_1, \dots, c'_n \in \mathbb{Z}_{>0}$ and a relation

$$\sum_{i=1}^n c'_i \rho_i = 0.$$

Set

$$c_i'' := c_i + pmc_i'$$

for some positive m so that $c_i'' > 0$ for all i . Let ς be the set of contact order $\{c_i''\rho_i\}_{i=1}^n$. Then

- $\sum_{i=1}^n c_i''\rho_i = 0$, so (2) is satisfied,
- For every i , $c_i'' = c_i \pmod{p}$. In particular, none of the c_1'', \dots, c_d'' is divisible by p as it is also the case for c_1, \dots, c_d by construction of $c_B = (c_1, \dots, c_d)$.

Furthermore, given that ρ_1, \dots, ρ_d form a \mathbb{Z} -basis of $N = \mathbb{Z}^d$ (the ambient lattice defining the toric variety X) by hypothesis, $\det(c_1''\rho_1, \dots, c_d''\rho_d) = \pm \prod_{i=1}^d c_i''$. As none of the c_1'', \dots, c_d'' is divisible by p ,

$$\text{rank}(c_1''\rho_1, \dots, c_n''\rho_n) = \text{rank}(c_1''\rho_1, \dots, c_d''\rho_d) = d.$$

Therefore (3) is satisfied for ς . Denote

$$M := \mathbb{Z}\langle c_1''\rho_1, \dots, c_d''\rho_d \rangle \subset M' := \mathbb{Z}\langle c_1''\rho_1, \dots, c_n''\rho_n \rangle.$$

Then

$$(5) \quad [\mathbb{Z}^d : M] = [\mathbb{Z}^d : M'] [M' : M].$$

Since ρ_1, \dots, ρ_d is a basis of \mathbb{Z}^d , we have $\mathbb{Z}^d/M \cong \bigoplus_{i=1}^d \mathbb{Z}/c_i''\mathbb{Z}$. Since $p \nmid \prod_{i=1}^d c_i''$, it follows from (5) that \mathbb{Z}^d/M' has no p -torsion. Therefore, (4) is satisfied for ς . We conclude that (X, Δ_ϵ) is separably Campana rationally connected using Lemma 3.2 and Theorem 2.8.

Finally, we note that the c_i'' may be chosen arbitrarily large. In particular, in the non-absolute non-klt case, we may add sufficiently large multiples of pc_i' to each c_i so that the resulting contact orders c_i'' along Δ_i are greater than the corresponding multiplicities m_i . □

Lemma 3.2. *With the notations of the previous theorem, $v \in V$ with all coordinates non-zero in \mathbb{F}_p exists.*

Proof. First, we show that for each coordinate index $i = 1, \dots, d$, the projection $\pi_i \circ \Phi$ to the i -th coordinate is not identically zero in V . This is equivalent to the i -th row of $-\overline{B}^{-1}\overline{A}$ not being identically zero. Set $\overline{C} := \overline{B}^{-1}\overline{A}$. Then the columns of \overline{C} express the rays $\overline{\rho}_{d+1}, \dots, \overline{\rho}_n$ in the basis given by the rays $\overline{\rho}_1, \dots, \overline{\rho}_d$. The i -th row of \overline{C} is then the i -th coordinates of the rays $\overline{\rho}_{d+1}, \dots, \overline{\rho}_n$ in that basis, for $1 \leq i \leq d$. We show that any row of \overline{C} cannot be identically zero. Indeed, assume it is the case. It implies that $\overline{\rho}_{d+1}, \dots, \overline{\rho}_n \in \langle \overline{\rho}_1, \dots, \widehat{\rho}_i, \dots, \overline{\rho}_d \rangle$.

Denote $\sigma = \text{cone}(\rho_1, \dots, \rho_d)$. Then, $\text{cone}(\rho_1, \dots, \widehat{\rho}_i, \dots, \rho_d)$ is a codimension-1 face and since X is complete, it is contained in two distinct maximal cones: σ and

$$\tau_i = \text{cone}(\rho_1, \dots, \widehat{\rho}_i, \dots, \rho_d, \widetilde{\rho}_i)$$

with $\widetilde{\rho}_i \in \{\rho_{d+1}, \dots, \rho_n\}$. Given that τ_i is a maximal cone,

$$\{\rho_1, \dots, \widehat{\rho}_i, \dots, \rho_d, \widetilde{\rho}_i\}$$

is a \mathbb{Z} -bases of N by smoothness of X . In particular,

$$\det(\overline{\rho}_1, \dots, \widehat{\rho}_i, \dots, \overline{\rho}_d, \widetilde{\rho}_i)$$

is a unit in \mathbb{F}_p . Therefore, $\overline{\rho}_1, \dots, \widehat{\rho}_i, \dots, \overline{\rho}_d, \widetilde{\rho}_i$ is an \mathbb{F}_p -basis of \mathbb{F}_p^d , which yields a contradiction.

For each i , let $H_i = \{x = (x_1, \dots, x_d) \in (\mathbb{F}_p)^d : x_i \equiv 0\}$. By the discussion above, each $V \cap H_i$ is a proper linear subspace of V . By classical linear algebra, a finite-dimensional vector space

over a field cannot be the union of finitely many proper linear subspaces. Hence

$$V \not\subset \bigcup_{i=1}^d (V \cap H_i),$$

so there exists $v = (v_1, \dots, v_d) \in V$ with $v_i \neq 0 \pmod{p}$ for all $i = 1, \dots, d$. \square

The proof of Theorem 3.1 shows that separable rational connectedness can be obtained under weaker assumptions than full smoothness.

Corollary 3.3. *Let (X, Δ_ϵ) be a Campana toric orbifold. Suppose there exists a smooth cone in the fan Σ of X such that all of its adjacent cones are smooth. Then (X, Δ_ϵ) is separably Campana rationally connected.*

Remark 3.4. The proof of Theorem 3.1 shows, in particular, that every projective toric variety is rationally connected (this follows from the datum of the coefficients c_i' together with Theorem 2.8). Moreover, it says that every Campana toric orbifold -whether klt or non-klt- is Campana rationally connected.

Remark 3.5. Let (X, Δ_ϵ) be a Campana toric orbifold. Let $\tilde{X} \rightarrow X$ be a toric blow-up and let $\tilde{\Delta}$ be the toric boundary of \tilde{X} . Then if (X, Δ_ϵ) is separably Campana rationally connected by good contact orders, so is $(\tilde{X}, \tilde{\Delta}_\epsilon)$. Indeed, for this we simply keep the same set of marked points and contact orders.

Example 3.6. Every smooth projective Campana non-klt orbifold surface is separably Campana rationally connected by good contact orders. This follows from the fact that every smooth projective toric surface is a toric blow up of \mathbb{P}^2 or a Hirzebruch surface, which are both separably Campana rationally connected by good contact orders.

4. SINGULAR CAMPANA NON-KLT TORIC ORBIFOLD

4.1. Singular non-klt Campana toric surface. In the previous section we have seen that every smooth non-klt Campana toric surface orbifold is separably Campana rationally connected. This suggests that any failure of separable Campana rational connectedness may be related to singularities. In this section, we characterize the toric surfaces that are Campana rationally connected in terms of the configuration of their rays (cf. Proposition 4.1). In Theorem 4.6, we further describe this property in terms of their singularities. Again, we work over an algebraically closed field \mathbf{k} of characteristic $p > 0$.

Proposition 4.1. *Let (X, Δ_ϵ) be a non-klt Campana toric surface orbifold. Let ρ_1, \dots, ρ_n be the primitive rays. If we can choose an \mathbb{F}_p -basis $\{\bar{u}, \bar{v}\}$ of the \mathbb{F}_p -vector space generated by $\bar{\rho}_1, \dots, \bar{\rho}_n$, with $\bar{u}, \bar{v} \in \{\bar{\rho}_1, \dots, \bar{\rho}_n\}$ such that*

- *either there exists k such that $\bar{\rho}_k = a_k \bar{u} + b_k \bar{v}$, with $a_k, b_k \neq 0 \pmod{p}$,*
- *or neither \bar{u} nor \bar{v} are alone in their direction among the reduction of the primitive rays mod p .*

Then (X, Δ_ϵ) is separably Campana rationally connected.

To prove the proposition, we first begin with the following lemma:

Lemma 4.2. *Let (X, Δ_ϵ) be a non-klt Campana toric surface orbifold. Let ρ_1, \dots, ρ_n be the primitive rays. If there exists $(\bar{c}_1, \dots, \bar{c}_n) \in (\mathbb{F}_p)^n$ such that*

- (a) $\sum_{i=1}^n \bar{c}_i \rho_i \equiv 0$,
- (b) *and indices $i \neq j$ such that $\overline{\bar{c}_i \bar{c}_j \det(\rho_i, \rho_j)} \neq 0$,*

then (X, Δ_ϵ) is separably Campana rationally connected.

Proof. We will prove that $(\bar{c}_1, \dots, \bar{c}_n) \in (\mathbb{F}_p)^n$ lifts into an element $(c_1, \dots, c_n) \in (\mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0})^n$ such that

- $\sum_{i=1}^n c_i \rho_i = 0$,
- the lattice M generated by $c_1 \rho_1, \dots, c_n \rho_n$ has rank 2, and
- \mathbb{Z}^2/M has no p -torsion,

then apply Theorem 2.8. As shown in the proof of Theorem 3.1, since we can choose c_i arbitrary large, we can reduce to the case where (X, Δ_e) is absolute non-plt. Consider the linear map:

$$\begin{aligned} R_2 : \mathbb{Z}^n &\rightarrow \mathbb{Z}^2 \\ v_i &\mapsto \rho_i \end{aligned}$$

(with $\{v_i\}_i$ the canonical basis of \mathbb{Z}^n). Consider the Smith normal form of the matrix of R_2 where the column are given by the rays of X :

$$\begin{bmatrix} d_1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & d_2 & 0 & \dots 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

By hypothesis, $p \nmid \det(\rho_i, \rho_j)$ for some pair (i, j) and by definition, d_2 (hence d_1) divides all the 2×2 minors of R_2 , hence $\det(\rho_i, \rho_j)$. Therefore, $p \nmid d_1 d_2$. Hence the reduction map

$$\ker_{\mathbb{Z}}(R_2) \rightarrow \ker_{\mathbb{F}_p}(\bar{R}_2)$$

is surjective and we can lift $(\bar{c}_1, \dots, \bar{c}_n) \in \ker_{\mathbb{F}_p}(R_2)$ into an element $(c_1, \dots, c_n) \in \ker_{\mathbb{Z}}(R_2)$ with all coordinates strictly positive by Lemma 4.3. In particular, we have

$$\sum_{i=1}^n c_i \rho_i = 0.$$

Denote M the lattice generated by $c_1 \rho_1, \dots, c_n \rho_n$. Since there is a pair (i, j) such that c_i, c_j , and $\det(\rho_i, \rho_j)$ are nonzero, the rank of M is 2. In addition, the assumption $\bar{c}_i \bar{c}_j \det(\rho_i, \rho_j) \neq 0$ implies that \mathbb{Z}^2/M has no p -torsion. \square

Lemma 4.3. *Let the $2 \times n$ matrix*

$$UR_2V = D = \begin{bmatrix} d_1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & d_2 & 0 & \dots 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

be the Smith normal form of the matrix of R_2 , with $U, V \in GL(\mathbb{Z})$. If $p \nmid d_1 d_2$, then the reduction map

$$\ker_{\mathbb{Z}}(R_2) \rightarrow \ker_{\mathbb{F}_p}(\bar{R}_2)$$

is surjective. In addition, we can choose the lift with all coordinates strictly positive.

Proof. Since $U, V \in GL(\mathbb{Z})$, we have $\det(U), \det(V) = \pm 1$. Let $\bar{y} \in \ker_{\mathbb{F}_p}(\bar{R}_2)$ so that $\bar{R}_2 \bar{y} = 0$. Write $\bar{y} = \bar{V} \bar{z}$. Then

$$(6) \quad \overline{UR_2V} \bar{z} = \overline{UR_2} \bar{y} = 0.$$

Write $\bar{z} := (\bar{z}_1, \dots, \bar{z}_n)$. Since $d_1, d_2 \neq 0 \pmod p$, we have $\bar{z}_1 = \bar{z}_2 = 0$ by (6). Choose a lift $z = (z_1, \dots, z_n) \in \mathbb{Z}^n$ of \bar{z} such that $z_1 = z_2 = 0$. Hence $Dz = 0$. Therefore

$$R_2(Vz) = U^{-1}Dz = 0,$$

and thus $Vz \in \ker_{\mathbb{Z}}(R_2)$. Write $Vz = (a_1, \dots, a_n)$. As in the proof of Theorem 3.1, by completeness of X , there exists $(b_1, \dots, b_n) \in \mathbb{Z}_{>0}^n$ such that $\sum_{i=1}^n b_i \rho_i = 0$. Set $c_i := a_i + pm b_i$ for $m \gg 0$ so that all $c_i > 0$. Then $y = (c_1, \dots, c_n)$ is such a lift. \square

Proof of Proposition 4.1. It suffices to show that the hypothesis of the proposition is equivalent to that of Lemma 4.2:

- Lemma 4.2 \implies Proposition 4.1: the assumption $\det(\rho_i, \rho_j) \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ for some pair (i, j) implies that $\text{rank}(\overline{\rho}_1, \dots, \overline{\rho}_n) = 2$. Let (i, j) be the pair in Lemma 4.2 and set $\overline{u} = \overline{\rho}_i$ and $\overline{v} = \overline{\rho}_j$. If the first assumption of (b) is not satisfied, then because $\sum_{i=1}^n \overline{c}_i \overline{\rho}_i = 0$ and $\overline{c}_i, \overline{c}_j \neq 0$, the second assumption has to be satisfied.
- Proposition 4.1 \implies Lemma 4.2: Set $\overline{u} = \overline{\rho}_m$ and $\overline{v} = \overline{\rho}_n$. In the first case of (b), we set $\overline{c}_m = -a_k, \overline{c}_n = -b_k, \overline{c}_k = 1$ and $\overline{c}_l = 0$ for all other l . Then the assumptions of Lemma 4.2 are satisfied with $(i, j) = (m, n)$. In the second case of (b), assume there is $\overline{\rho}_s = a_s \overline{u}$ and $\overline{\rho}_t = a_t \overline{v}$ with $a_s, a_t \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p}$. We set $\overline{c}_m = -a_s, \overline{c}_n = -a_t, \overline{c}_s = \overline{c}_t = 1$ and $\overline{c}_k = 0$ otherwise. Then the assumptions of Lemma 4.2 are satisfied with $(i, j) = (m, n)$.

□

4.1.1. *Singularities of toric surfaces in characteristic p .* Our next goal is to study the property of being separably Campana rationally connected in terms of the singularities of the Campana toric surface orbifold. We first classify toric surface singularities into *wild* and *tame*.

Recall that all toric surface singularities are quotient singularities of the form $\frac{1}{m}(1, a)$. More specifically, if two rays u, v induce a non-smooth 2-dimensional cone which corresponds to a singular point of the form $\frac{1}{m}(1, a)$, then locally the surface is isomorphic to \mathbb{A}^2/μ_m (the geometric quotient) where μ_m acts on the diagonal weighted by $(1, a)$.

Definition 4.4. We say that a quotient singularity of the form $\frac{1}{m}(1, a)$ is *wild* if $p|m$. Otherwise, we say that it is *tame*. We say that a non-smooth 2-dimensional cone σ is *wildly* (resp. *tamely*) singular if the corresponding quotient singularity is wild (resp. tame).

We can also relate the singularity of a cone to the configuration of its rays. If \underline{X} is a toric surface and ρ, ρ' are two adjacent rays spanning a cone σ , then we have:

- If $\det(u_\rho, u_{\rho'}) = 1$, then σ is smooth.
- If $p \nmid \det(u_\rho, u_{\rho'})$ and $\det(u_\rho, u_{\rho'}) \neq 1$, then σ is tamely singular.
- If $p \mid \det(u_\rho, u_{\rho'})$, then σ is wildly singular.

Example 4.5. [Weighted projective surface] Let $N = \mathbb{Z}^2$ be a lattice spanned by $e_1 = (1, 0)$ and $e_2 = (0, 1)$. Let Σ be the fan spanned by the following rays:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_1 &= e_1 \\ \rho_2 &= e_2 \\ \rho_3 &= -e_1 - p e_2 \end{aligned}$$

Then the toric variety corresponding to Σ is the weighted projective plane $\mathbb{P}(1, 1, p)$. Note that the cone spanned by ρ_1 and ρ_3 is wildly singular, while the two other cones are smooth.

Let ς be the collection of contact orders consisting of

$$\begin{aligned} c_1 &= e_1 \\ c_2 &= p e_2 \\ c_3 &= -e_1 - p e_2 \end{aligned}$$

Let N' be the sub-lattice $\mathbb{Z} \cdot \varsigma \subset N$ and let Σ' be the fan induced by the rays that the c_i 's span in N' . Since $c_3 = -c_1 - c_2$, the toric surface induced by Σ' is \mathbb{P}^2 . The natural inclusion $N' \subset N$ induces an inclusion on the dual lattices $M \subset M'$, which induces a toric morphism

$\phi : X' \rightarrow X$ given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}^2 &\rightarrow \mathbb{P}(1, 1, p) \\ (x : y : z) &\mapsto (x : y : z^p) \end{aligned}$$

This morphism is compatible with the action of μ_p on \mathbb{P}^2

$$((x : y : z), \zeta) \mapsto (x : y : \zeta z).$$

Since $\mathbf{k}[x, y, z]^{\mu_p} = \mathbf{k}[x, y, z^p]$, one checks that this induces an isomorphism

$$\mathbb{P}^2 / \mu_p \simeq \mathbb{P}(1, 1, p),$$

where the left hand side is the geometric quotient.

Theorem 4.6. *Let (X, Δ_ϵ) be a non-klt Campana toric surface orbifold. If any ray ρ has a non-adjacent cone which is either smooth or tamely singular, then (X, Δ_ϵ) is separably Campana rationally connected.*

Proof. Let ρ_1, \dots, ρ_n be the rays of \underline{X} . According to Proposition 4.1, if (X, Δ_ϵ) is not separably Campana rationally connected, then we are in the following two cases:

- either $\text{rank}(\overline{\rho}_1, \dots, \overline{\rho}_n) = 1$, or
- $\text{rank}(\overline{\rho}_1, \dots, \overline{\rho}_n) = 2$ and if $\{\overline{u}, \overline{v}\} \subset \{\overline{\rho}_1, \dots, \overline{\rho}_n\}$ is an \mathbb{F}_p -basis of \mathbb{F}_p^2 , then every other $\overline{\rho}_i$ lies in the same direction of either \overline{u} or \overline{v} .

In the first scenario, if $\text{rank}(\overline{\rho}_1, \dots, \overline{\rho}_n) = 1$, then for any cone spanned by two adjacent rays ρ_i and ρ_j , we have $\det(\rho_i, \rho_j) \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$, i.e. all 2-dimensional cones are wildly singular.

In the second scenario, without loss of generality, suppose $\overline{u} = \overline{\rho}_1$. Let u be the ray corresponding to \overline{u} . Assume that every $\overline{\rho}_i$ with $i \neq 1$ lies in the direction of \overline{v} . Hence $\det(\overline{\rho}_i, \overline{\rho}_j) \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ for all $i, j \neq 1$. This suggests that if σ is a cone of \underline{X} not containing u , then σ is wildly singular. Hence in both scenarios, there exists a ray ρ among the ρ_i 's such that any cone not containing ρ is wildly singular. \square

Remark 4.7. If \underline{X} has more than four rays, the assumption of the previous theorem is equivalent to the existence of two non-adjacent cones in the fan of \underline{X} which are either smooth or tamely singular. If \underline{X} has strictly less than four rays, this is equivalent to no cone being wildly singular.

The converse of Theorem 4.6 does not hold. In fact, by Remark 3.5 it is enough to check separable Campana rational connectedness on a blow-down.

Corollary 4.8. *Let (X, Δ_ϵ) be a non-klt Campana toric surface orbifold. Suppose that there is a toric blow-up $\underline{X} \rightarrow \underline{X}'$ such that for any ray $\rho' \in \Sigma'$, ρ' has a non-adjacent cone which is either smooth or tamely singular, then (X, Δ_ϵ) is separably Campana rationally connected.*

Remark 4.9. If \underline{X} is a projective toric surface with three adjacent smooth cones, (X, Δ_ϵ) is separably Campana rationally connected by Theorem 4.6, which we already knew from Corollary 3.3.

4.2. Weighted projective space. In this section, we prove Theorem 1.4. We first recall the description of a weighted projective space as a toric variety.

Definition 4.10. We call an unordered tuple of positive integers (q_0, \dots, q_n) a well-formed weight if $n \geq 1$ and any set of n elements among the q_i 's are coprime.

Let $Q = (q_0, \dots, q_n)$ be a well-formed weight. Let v_0, \dots, v_n be vectors in \mathbb{Z}^n generating the fan of \mathbb{P}^n (recall that $\sum_{i=0}^n v_i = 0$). Set

$$e_i = \frac{1}{q_i} \cdot v_i.$$

In particular, $\sum_{i=0}^n q_i e_i = 0$. Let N be the lattice generated by the e_i 's. A weighted projective space $\mathbb{P}(Q) = \mathbb{P}(q_0, \dots, q_n)$ is the toric variety associated to the fan Σ in $N_{\mathbb{R}}$ whose cones are generated by all proper subsets of $\{e_0, \dots, e_n\}$.

Remark 4.11. Note that the general definition of a weighted projective space $\mathbb{P}(Q)$ does not require Q to be well-formed. Nevertheless, we can normalize the weights so that any two weighted projective spaces $\mathbb{P}(Q)$ and $\mathbb{P}(Q')$ are isomorphic if and only if the normalized weights $\overline{Q} = \overline{Q'}$, see for example [AA89].

Denote by ρ_i the ray spanned by e_i .

Theorem 4.12. *Let (X, Δ) be an absolute non-klt Campana toric orbifold such that \underline{X} is a weighted projective space $\mathbb{P}(Q)$, with $Q = (q_0, \dots, q_n)$ a well-formed weight, and Δ its toric boundary divisor. Then if $\text{char } k$ divides any of the q_i 's, (X, Δ) is not separably Campana rationally connected.*

Proof. Let $\varsigma = \{c_i\}_{i=0}^k$ be a set of contact orders making (X, Δ) Campana rationally connected. Since it satisfies the balancing condition and (X, Δ) is absolute non-klt, it follows that $k = n$ and $c_i \in \rho_i$ up to ordering. Suppose $c_n = \frac{b_n}{a_n} \cdot v_n$ with $\gcd(a_n, b_n) = 1$, $a_n > 1$. Since $v_0 + \dots + v_n = 0$, we have

$$c_n = -\frac{b_n}{a_n} \cdot (v_0 + \dots + v_{n-1}).$$

The balancing condition and the fact that v_0, \dots, v_{n-1} is a basis of \mathbb{Z}^n implies that $c_i = \frac{b_n}{a_n} \cdot v_i = \frac{q_i b_n}{a_n} \cdot e_i$ for $i = 0, \dots, n-1$. Since the c_i 's are lattice points of N , we must have $\frac{q_i b_n}{a_n} \in \mathbb{Z}$ for all $i = 0, \dots, n-1$, i.e. $a_n \mid \gcd(q_0, \dots, q_{n-1})$. Since Q is well-formed, $a_n = 1$. Hence we have that c_i is an integral multiple of v_i for each $i = 0, \dots, n$. Therefore, any set of contact orders making (X, Δ) Campana rationally connected is of the form

$$(7) \quad \varsigma_m := \{m \cdot v_0, \dots, m \cdot v_n\}$$

for some non-zero integer m . We will prove that ς_m does not make (X, Δ) separably Campana rationally connected. Fix m . Let $\pi : \mathcal{U} \rightarrow W$, $ev : \mathcal{U} \rightarrow X$ be the family of non-degenerate stable log maps with contact orders ς_m as above. We want to show that the dominant map $ev^{(2)}$ is not separable:

$$\begin{aligned} ev^{(2)} : \mathbb{P}^1 \times \mathbb{P}^1 \times W &\rightarrow \mathbb{P}(Q) \times \mathbb{P}(Q) \\ (x_1, x_2, f_w : \mathbb{P}^1 \rightarrow X) &\mapsto (f_w(x_1), f_w(x_2)) \end{aligned}$$

By [Har77, Proposition III.10.4], a morphism between smooth varieties $h : Y \rightarrow Z$ over an algebraically closed field is smooth if and only if for every closed point $y \in Y$, the induced map on tangent spaces $dh_y : T_{Y,y} \rightarrow T_{Z,h(y)}$ is surjective. Moreover, a separable morphism is smooth at the generic point. Therefore, to prove our theorem, it is enough to show that there exists a dense open subset V of $\mathbb{P}^1 \times \mathbb{P}^1 \times W$ such that $dev_v^{(2)}$ is not surjective for any closed point $v \in V$.

Let $U \subset \mathbb{P}(Q) \times \mathbb{P}(Q)$ denote the open dense smooth locus and let $V := (ev^{(2)})^{-1}(U) \subset \mathbb{P}^1 \times \mathbb{P}^1 \times W$. Let $f_w : \mathbb{P}^1 \rightarrow X$ be a fiber of ev , i.e. a non-degenerate stable log map with contact orders ς_m . Consider the inseparable map

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_n : \mathbb{P}^n &\rightarrow \mathbb{P}(Q) \\ (x_0 : \dots : x_n) &\mapsto (x_0^{q_0} : \dots : x_n^{q_n}) \end{aligned}$$

Then there exists a map $\tilde{f}_w : \mathbb{P}^1 \rightarrow \mathbb{P}^n$ such that $f_w = \phi_n \circ \tilde{f}_w$. Indeed, Let s, t be the coordinate of \mathbb{P}^1 . Denote by $p_\infty = [1 : 0] \in \mathbb{P}^1$. Then we may write $\mathbb{P}^1 = p_\infty \cup \mathbb{A}_{s/t}^1$. Let

$$\{p_i = [s_i : t_i]\}_{i=0}^n \subset \mathbb{P}^1$$

be the points such that $f_w(p_i) \in \Delta_i$, where Δ_i is the boundary divisor corresponding to ρ_i . Without loss of generality, we may assume that p_∞ is not one of the p_i 's. Let x_i denote the equation of Δ_i . It follows from (7) that

$$f^*x_i = \lambda_i(ts_i - st_i)^{mq_i}$$

for $\lambda_i \in \mathbf{k}^\times$. Then, as in the proof of [CLT25, Theorem 8.2], the λ_i 's, and hence the map f_w is uniquely determined by the image of $f(p_\infty) \in G_m^n$. We construct a lift $\tilde{f}_w : \mathbb{P}^1 \rightarrow \mathbb{P}^n$ by setting

$$\tilde{f}_w^*x_i = (\lambda_i)^{1/q_i}(ts_i - st_i)^m$$

We see that $f_w = \phi_n \circ \tilde{f}_w$. Therefore, we get a factorization:

$$\text{ev}_{|V}^{(2)} : V \xrightarrow{\psi} (\mathbb{P}^n \times \mathbb{P}^n)_{|U} \xrightarrow{\phi_n^{(2)}} U,$$

We then have

$$\text{dev}^{(2)} = d\phi_n^{(2)} \circ d\psi.$$

Since ϕ_n is not smooth over the generic point in characteristic p dividing one of the q_j , this completes the proof. \square

Remark 4.13. Notice that if p divides any of the q_j 's, $N/\mathbb{Z} \cdot \varsigma_m$ contains p -torsion. Indeed, denote by M the lattice generated by $q_0e_0, \dots, q_n e_n$ and $L = \mathbb{Z} \cdot \varsigma_m$. Since $L \subset M \subset N$, we have

$$[N : L] = [N : M][M : L].$$

Furthermore, since $\sum_{i=0}^n q_i e_i = \sum_{i=0}^n v_i = 0$, we have

$$[N : M] = \prod_{i=0}^n q_i$$

by [RT12, Lemma 1]. Therefore, $q_i | [N : L]$ for all $i \in \{0, \dots, n\}$. In particular, Theorem 2.8 does not apply.

Example 4.14. Let $(\mathbb{P}(Q), \Delta)$ be an absolute non-klt Campana toric orbifold as in Theorem 4.12, and let p be a prime dividing one of the q_i 's. Then we can construct explicitly a toric blow-up

$$\tilde{X} \longrightarrow \mathbb{P}(Q),$$

with $\tilde{\Delta}$ the toric boundary divisor of \tilde{X} and such that $(\tilde{X}, \tilde{\Delta})$, seen as an absolute non-klt Campana toric orbifold, is separably Campana rationally connected with good contact orders. There are two cases to consider:

- (1) If $Q = (1, \dots, 1, q_n)$, we add the ray $e_{n+1} = -e_n$ and subdivide the fan accordingly. Let \tilde{X} be the resulting toric variety and $\tilde{\Delta}$ its toric boundary divisor. We define the set ς of contact orders as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} c_i &= e_i & \text{for } i \in \{0, \dots, n-1\}, \\ c_n &= (q_n + 1)e_n, \\ c_{n+1} &= -e_n = e_{n+1}. \end{aligned}$$

By Theorem 2.8, $(\tilde{X}, \tilde{\Delta})$ is separably Campana rationally ζ -connected with good contact orders. For instance, when the toric variety is $\mathbb{P}(1, 1, p)$, this blow-up produces the Hirzebruch surface.

- (2) Otherwise, we add the ray $e_{n+1} = -\sum_{i=0}^n e_i$ and subdivide. In this case, we can check that the induced toric variety \tilde{X} is a non-trivial blow-up of X . We define the set ζ of contact orders to be $c_i = e_i$ for all i , and using Theorem 2.8, we verify that $(\tilde{X}, \tilde{\Delta})$ is separably Campana rationally ζ -connected with good contact orders.

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